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Human Resource Development (HRD) and Organizational Performance: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Every organization desires success. Success is the primary goal of establishing organizations, both public and private. In the present reality of the world, especially in developing economies, many organizations are going into extinction even in the face of adequate capital and financial resources. This thesis, therefore, analyzed the role of human resource development as a catalyst to organizational performance. A qualitative and descriptive content analysis research approach was adopted in the study. The outcome was that most organizations still standing in a turbulent world economy have imbibed some elements of human resource development (HRD) such as constant staff training, development, coaching, and mentoring. Their investment in HRD has become a catalyst for a resounding performance of their organization and is recommended for every public and private enterprise.

Keywords: Human resource development, Performance, Organizations, Catalyst, human capital.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the bedrock and soul of any organization. Nwanolue and Iwuoha (2012) described it as the strength of an organization. The success or failure of any human endeavour is fundamentally dependent on the functional disposition of the human beings found in such arrangement (Nwanolue and Iwuoha, 2012). Consequently, businesses, governments and every other endeavour have come to factor human resources as a force to reckon with in the drive towards maximization of productivity and performance.

An organization's human resources comprise both men and women, young and elderly, who work for the company, producing things and providing services. They are an organization's most valuable assets (Ezeani, 2002). In that premise, every organization needs to build capacity in its human resources if organizational performance is to be assured. Building human resource capacity translates to human resource development. According to Agwu and Ogiriki (2014), human resource development is the combined application of career development, organizational development, and training and development to increase the effectiveness of individuals, groups, and organizations. Agwu and Ogiriki (2014) also noted that HRD methods improve employees' abilities, attitudes, and behaviour, directly or indirectly improving organizational performance.

Every organization is desirous of good performance by its staff. Staff performance is an outcome of various inputs by organizations, including human resources and capital development. In that premise, the

performance of staff is a direct response to these inputs. Aiya, Omoregie, and Ogbeide (2015) reveal, for instance, that an organization's performance processes are enhanced by well-coordinated HRD practices and that each employee's participation has a greater impact on the outcomes the organization achieves. A solid HRD practice increases staff productivity, which in turn improves organizational performance (Aiya, Omoregie, and Ogbeide, 2015).

Empirical studies, according to Chukwuma (2015), have shown that poor human resource development leads to low productivity and performance. Sarah, Bello, and Erunke (2022) in that regard posit that HRD practices remain a major factor in determining the performance of employees in organizations. Orga and Ogbo (2012) advised that organizations must emphasize attracting, training, developing, and retaining talent to ensure sterling performance and avoid dire consequences as their competitors may outplay them. With the increase in competition, Orga and Ogbo (2012) argue that organizations must become more adaptable, resilient, agile, customer-focused, and imbued with other human resources development practices to succeed.

In that regard, human resource or capital is dynamic and leads to the realization of the potential inherent in human development which is the key to organizational and economic development (Gruzina et al, 2021; Piwowar-Sulej, 2021; Stock et al, 2018). Human resource development is progressive, incremental, multi-faceted, dynamic, and evolutionary (Onah et al, 2023). It requires constant individual improvements, which result in societal and industrial development. With human resource development, organizations are sure to improve, to make progress, and to change for the better, including higher income and better living standards for members of the organization.

Human capital or resource is an inestimable asset; that is, a factor of production on which all other productive assets or resources are dependent and are activated to serve their useful purposes (Onah et al, 2023). According to the authors, all developments witnessed by man right from civilization to the first and the fourth industrial revolutions are products of advancements in human resource development-knowledge, skills, education, training, and talents properly harnessed for the benefit of organizations and mankind. Human beings, therefore, as determinants of what becomes of their organizations according to Onah et al (2023), need to engage in constant training, education, learning, and skill acquisition in the bid to acquire capacities and experiences needed to actualize organizational success.

Against this backdrop, this thesis undertook to descriptively analyze the elements of human resource development and its catalytic impact on organizational performance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study adopted a qualitative and descriptive method. Through secondary sources comprising mainly of review of books, journal articles, internet resources, etc., germane data based on extant literature on organizational performance and human resource development were generated and critically analyzed per theme. This approach ensures the accuracy and authenticity of the data gathered and relevance in making informed judgments. In that regard, the researchers employed a contextual-explanatory-analysis approach in the interpretation of the qualitative data used. This enhances the validity and reliability of the study based on findings revealed by data from the extant literature. It is based on this analysis that discoveries on the subject matter were made and conclusions duly drawn.

Theoretical Framework of Analysis

The study adopts Jacob Mincer and Gary Becker's Human Capital Theory in the 1950s and 1960s as its theoretical foundation. The theory with the idea that capital is not limited to property and machinery, but also includes the learned and practical skills of every member of the community dates back to Adam Smith's era. Human capital is a resource that other resources depend on. Human capital emerges from skills, knowledge, education, experience, and abilities inherent in people. When these resources are available in organizational staff, Onah et al (2023) aver that those organizations gain a competitive advantage over their competitors. The authors maintain that for organizations to sustain their competitive advantage, they must develop a unique workforce with a special edge that rivals cannot easily get.

Therefore, investment in human capital development is based on education and training, which brings about productivity and innovation (Eze, 2010).

The relevance of Human Capital Theory cannot be overemphasized. It will help the management of organizations to assess how training and education relate to one another as inputs. The human capital theory offers policymakers a lens for evaluating the relative efficiency of investment in programmes that encourage more human capital development. The first tenet of the theory is on skills, qualifications, and education. Efficient service delivery and the productivity of employees are connected to their qualifications, education, and abilities. Organizations should invest in education in the same way that they do in equipment and machinery. That will increase production, training, and skills acquisition of workers. The second tenet of the theory calls for work experience, which results from the growth of human capital. The more development programmes workers undergo, the more experienced they are and the more they create value.

Elements of HRD

Training

The main goals of training were to help individuals of the organization learn the skills and information necessary to be great performers and to teach them how to do their existing duties (Jonas, George & Hill, 2000). According to Tharenou, Saks, and Moore (2007), it is the methodical acquisition and development of the information, skills, and attitude that workers need to do a task or job effectively or to perform better in the workplace. According to Beardwell and Holden (2001), training is a deliberate procedure to alter behaviour, attitude, or knowledge through learning experiences to perform effectively in any activity or a variety of activities. According to Stone (2002), training plays a significant part in any workforce's success.

Staff training should be more serious and sensitive to employees' training needs because organizations are only as good as their employees (Noe, 2008). According to Bratton and Gold (2000), successful companies understand that their employees are their greatest asset in the current business climate. In the light of this, Dim et al. (2019) contend that in order for workers to develop the knowledge, skills, and competences required to significantly contribute to the expansion of the company, they must receive substantial on-the-job training.

Just like blood is necessary for human existence, staff training is crucial to an organization's growth and development (Adelere, 2017). To support employees' growth and productivity in any firm, it is crucial to provide them with physical, social, intellectual, and mental training (Adelere, 2017). Accordingly, Philips et al. (n:d) in Adelere (2017) define training as a deliberate, organized, and coordinated approach to help employees acquire the skills and mindset that will optimize their current and future productivity and the overall efficacy of the business's operations. The goal of training, a type of specialized education, is to equip the learner with the specific knowledge, abilities, and mindset needed to succeed in a particular role (Adelere, 2017).

Peretomode et al (2001) defined training as a well-coordinated organizational effort or activities designed to assist an individual in gaining particular and immediately applicable skills, information, ideas, attitudes, and behaviours that will allow him to operate more effectively and efficiently in his current position. However, according to Obadan (2000), training is a specialized procedure that teaches people how to perform direct tasks of various complexities and develop required job behaviours. Accordingly, training is a procedure that boosts and enhances human efficiency by giving workers the chance to learn new skills and up-to-date information needed to perform a variety of specialized jobs at work (Adelere, 2017).

Development

According to Onasanya (2006), development is the notion that deals with special programs that are intended to educate and groom a worker with a certain level of education and training for higher responsibilities. Development is the process of becoming more intricate and complicated through continuous learning, whereas training is intended to give people the chance to master new abilities for

certain specialized tasks (Beardwell & Holden, 2001). According to Rouda and Kusy (1995), development is the process of gaining information, skills, and abilities as well as embracing behaviours that enhance productivity at work.

Staff development is a procedure used in an economic system for hiring, choosing, training, inspiring, and requiring workers (Adelere, 2017). Staff development and training are usually used interchangeably, but they are not the same. Obisi (1996) differentiated them by observing that while training occurs because of a specific job purpose, development is broader and goes beyond specifics. The author stated that development includes both activities that lead to personality evolution and activities that enhance job effectiveness.

In contrast to training, which is a one-time change of events, staff development is essentially and primarily an educational process that is ongoing and lifelong. The word "development" refers to a person's entire growth. Accordingly, staff development encompasses not only better job performance but also better behaviour, knowledge, personality, and attitude. According to the Indian Ministry of Human Resources Development (MHRD, n.d.), it encompasses personal development and all methods used to enhance an employee's performance and conduct. According to Flippo in MHRD (n.d.), staff development includes not only gaining the competencies and skills required for one's current position but also the skills required for tasks in the future. These are the goals of staff development:

- Enhance workers' performance across the board.
- Determine which employees in the company have the necessary potential and train them for future promotions.
- Ensure that the necessary number of staff members are available to step in in the event of future emergencies.
- Keep faculty members from becoming stagnant by introducing them to the newest ideas and methods in their fields of expertise.
- Replace employees with highly skilled and academically educated experts who have advanced through the ranks.
- Enhance analytical skills and cognitive processes.
- Give employees the chance to achieve their professional goals.
- Gain a better understanding of human relations issues and enhance your interpersonal abilities (MHRD, n.d).

Bartlett (2001) sums up the conceptualization of employee development by claiming that development is a non-stop progression that affects positively employees' growth. The author argues that money invested in development of staff is money well invested as it will increase employees' performance.

Coaching

Sridanan (2016) notes that coaching is frequently seen as a beneficial instrument for the development of both individuals and organizations. It is a technique deemed suitable for raising awareness among both individuals and teams to attain satisfactory work outcomes (Minor, 2007). According to Mathis and Jackson in Nuryanti et al. (2018), coaching is an action a leader does to help followers perform better. According to Minor (2007), fostering goal accomplishment in the organization is a component of coaching. Fostering is a guiding procedure that a manager uses to teach and orient a worker about the realities of the workplace so that they can overcome any barriers to performing at their best.

It is anticipated that organizations that implement coaching would be able to enhance their organization. Coaching is regarded as a learning process to increase individual capacity in which a process of varied knowledge to create behaviour occurs (Nuryanti et al, 2018). Mathis and Jackson in Nuryanti et al. (2018) noted that a solid rapport between the coached and the coaches is a necessary component of effective coaching. According to Kampa-Kolesch and Anderson (2001), coaching is a type of systematic feedback intervention intended to improve interpersonal awareness, professional abilities, and individual effectiveness. In that light, Gil and Carrillo (2013) see coaching as a process that gives people the resources, information, and chances they require for both professional growth and increased effectiveness.

Coaching, according to Colomo and Casado (2006), is a directed, planned, and ongoing improvement process that helps participants get closer to the ideal performance that is required of them in their roles within an organization. According to Colomo and Casado (2006), coaching is a dialogue that takes place in a constructive, goal-oriented setting between a coach and a subordinate. Bono, Purvanova, Oowler, and David (2009) aver that some authors concur that coaching is a process that entails several one-on-one encounters between a manager and a subordinate staff being coached. To Feldman and Lankan (2005), coaching is a relationship that entails one-on-one discussion about issues of the workplace.

Additionally, coaching is a collaboration between a management-level client and a coach employed by an organization to help the employee become a more successful and effective manager (Hannafey and Vitulano, 2013). According to Utrilla, Grande, and Lorenzo (2015), coaching is a process created by an organization that involves a coach and a coachee. Its goals are to improve the coachee's skills and abilities to support career growth and to address issues linked to work performance.

Brockbank and McGill (2006) defined it as an individual's learning and development that leads to change. The authors went on to say that coaching is a straightforward yet powerful method of personal development in which the coach and client form a partnership that fosters and maintains the client's competence and personal development. In that process, the clients sacrifice who they are to become who they wish to be (Brockbank & McGill, 2006). Therefore, it becomes the coach's responsibility to identify and unleash that potential in the subordinate being coached.

Mentoring

It is a truism that skilled and committed employees are the only sustainable source of competitive advantage an organization has (Mayfield and Mayfield, 2007). To ensure that the organization remains competitive, Oladimeji and Sowemimo (2020) assert that mentoring employees must be ensured and strengthened. Mentoring ensures that less experienced workers can adapt to the ways of an organization (Monika and Nischay, 2017).

The act of giving mentees the chance to improve their performance at work is known as mentoring. It is acknowledged that mentoring has a major impact on the growth of businesses (Oladimeji and Sowemimo, 2020). Mentoring is a semi-structured guiding system in which an individual or group of individuals shares their expertise to help others advance in their lives and careers (Allens, 2007).

Professional relationships enable an inexperienced person, known as a mentee, to receive assistance from another person, this time an experienced person known as the mentor, in acquiring the particular knowledge and skills required to enhance the inexperienced person's professional development (Pertin, 2011).

According to Murray (2006), mentoring is a connection that can lead to better organizational outcomes and good development. In addition to giving managers and executives a productive and successful way to help groups of employees gain the knowledge and skills necessary to function in a changing business environment, mentoring offers a forum for giving candid, constructive advice to support the career development of recently hired employees (Griffin and Ayers, 2005). Mentoring improves self-confidence and job competitiveness, increases worker diversity, and entails encouragement, constructive criticism, openness, mutual trust, respect, and a willingness to learn and contribute (Oladimeji and Sowmimo, 2020). According to Shea (2007), mentoring is a loving, sharing, and developmental relationship in which one person invests time and expertise to advance the development, expertise, and talents of another. In that regard, Barkham (2005) notes that it ties the development of the mentor, the protégé, and the organization to both professional and personal growth. Mentoring is the informal transfer of information, social capital, and psychosocial support that the receiver believes is pertinent to their professional, career, or work development (Bozeman and Feeney, 2007). A significant individual developmental relationship between a mentor and a protégé is what many studies define as mentoring (Joiner, Bartram, and Garreffa, 2004; Ragins and Scandura, 1999).

Mentors play a crucial role in companies because they ensure that the knowledge required to position junior colleagues for improved performance and prepare them for organizational responsibilities is

transferred and continued (Allen, 2007, in Oladimeji and Sowemimo, 2020). On the other hand, Murray (2006) defines a mentee as an individual who is assisted by an expert but has less experience and understanding in a particular sector or task. According to Griffin and Ayers (2005), a mentee is a person in a mentoring relationship who gets advocacy, safety, and career assistance from a mentor. The mentors run the risk of retiring with the knowledge and expertise that the mentees require to enhance the performance of the business if mentoring tactics, including exposure, counselling, sponsorship, role modelling, and assignment, are not used. This is because when mentors retire and go from the company, the organization's vision, culture, internal and external networks, skills, and historical context will be lost (Peterson and Hicks, 2010). To maintain and preserve an organization's success, it is necessary to pass on the mentors' knowledge to the following generation. Therefore, mentoring is crucial to addressing an organization's loss of performance and knowledge (Oladimeji and Sowemimo, 2020).

Concept of Performance

Performance is typically defined as the degree to which an individual helps the company reach its objectives (Onafadeji, Ogunyemi, and Alarape, 2017). According to Armstrong (2002), performance is often evaluated in terms of results and conduct. According to Gungor (2011), performance encompasses the following: output quality, output quantity, output timeliness, attendance at work, and cooperativeness. To Onafadeji et al. (2017), employee performance may be summed up as the related tasks that are expected of an employee and the quality of those tasks. It's what a worker does or doesn't do.

Performance is what binds the various components of a business together so that it can operate as a unified entity (Osiobe, 2021). According to Ammons and Roenugk (2020), delegated decision authority is necessary for effective performance management. This implies that managers at the program level must be given the authority to make meaningful decisions. Based on that viewpoint, several things affect performance. Therefore, performance is defined as the organization's accomplishment of its objectives. It comprises results attained or accomplished as a result of teams' or individuals' contributions to the organization's strategic objectives (Antwi and Darkwa, 2021).

Camelia and Luminita (2013) separated the definition of performance into four stages. Profitability, productivity, inventiveness, flexibility, adaptation, growth, development, market penetration, planning, and staff quality were all included while evaluating performance between 1957 and 1979. From 1981 to 1994, an activity was considered successful if its objectives were met. Performance is therefore dependent on achieving several management-established objectives at this stage. Performance was evaluated in connection with production between 1995 and 2000. Performance has been measured in terms of value generation since 2000.

Price in Antwi and Darkwa (2021) noted that organizational effectiveness and performance are interchangeable. The author used productivity, conformity, and institutionalization as criteria to evaluate the performance of an activity. Again, Labrousse in Antwi and Darkwa (2021) characterizes performance as being a chain of attributes specific to (in case of a company): the company being able to cope with foreign competition, being able to quantify its productive effort at minimum costs and a company capable of exploiting a niche and establishing an important enlargement. Moh in Antwi and Darkwa (2021) further identify productivity, flexibility, and adaptability as criteria for evaluating performance. According to Gibson in Antwi and Darkwa (2021), performance can be evaluated based on productivity, efficiency, satisfaction, flexibility, development, and survival. Shashua and Goldschmidt in Antwi and Darkwa (2021) measured performance based on profit margin, share profitability, capital profitability, rate of operating capital, and rate of activity. Dubois in Antwi and Darkwa (2021) evaluates performance based on growth, profitability, productivity, liability, and solvency.

Performance is summarized as the actual output or outcomes as compared to the anticipated outputs during a given time frame. It concerns the results of a specific assignment or endeavour. Service delivery, work and skill knowledge, creativity in problem solving, collaboration with coworkers in problem solving, and dependability—that is, attendance and task completion—are all included (Olu-Ogunleye, Akinbode, Oyelude, & Ogunleye, 2022).

Aftermath of HRD:

Employee Commitment

Simply said, employee commitment refers to how committed an employee feels about their company (Meyer & Elyse, 2010; Dernovsek, 2008; & Zheng et al, 2010). According to Tzafrir and Baruch (2005), it is also regarded as the extent to which workers dedicate themselves to the company in terms of feeling a sense of belonging and being willing to take on difficulties. An essential component of enterprises is employee commitment (Timoti, 2020). To establish and maintain competitive advantage and performance, organizations depend on dedicated workers (Latham et al, 2008; Akintayo, 2010; & Tumwesigye, 2010). Employee commitment is essential for members of organizations and their organizations to function well in the ever-evolving business sector (Ivancevich, 2010; Andrew, 2017; and Albrecht, 2010). Employee engagement must be encouraged by any firm hoping to improve performance and efficiency (Gul, 2015; Markos and Sridhevi, 2010; Dost and Ahmed, 2011).

Whitener (2001) in Timoti (2020) alludes to this assertion by stating that maintaining a sustained competitive edge and increasing production depend heavily on that high degree of devotion. Employees with low-level commitment are not willing and will not give their best to their organizations (Dost and Ahmed, 2011). In that line, Mathotaarachchi et al (2018) assert that low levels of employee commitment are found in employees who do not give their best to their organizations but rather pursue personal success. Employees with low commitment are known for their eagerness to search and move to alternative jobs. They are equally ready to resign at the slightest excuse (Timoti, 2020). However, highly dedicated workers identify with the company and see themselves as an essential component of it (Lo et al, 2009; Mathotaarachchi et al, 2018). According to Brooks (2006), dedicated workers go above and beyond what is required of them by management. High levels of organizational commitment among employees result in high levels of performance and efficiency in their firms (Andrew, 2017).

Noraazian and Khalip (2016), drawing from Allen's (2007) three-part organizational commitment model, explained organizational commitment further. The three affective, continuance, and normative commitments are some of the constituents. When someone is emotionally invested in, identifies with, and participates more in the organization, this is known as affective commitment. It is a worker's emotional connection to the company (Balassiano and Salles, 2012; Andrew, 2017; Rhodes et al., 2001). Because their working relationship aligns with the organization's goals and values, employees with affective commitment traits are very loyal to the company and wish to remain there (Saygan, 2011; Wang et al, 2010; Gelaidan and Ahmad, 2013). Andrew (2017) underlined once more that workers who have a high emotional commitment stay with their companies because they want to.

When an employee chooses to remain with the company due to the time and resources previously invested in the company and after considering the expenses of changing occupations, this is known as continuity commitment (Umoh et al, 2014; Commeiras and Fournier, 2001). The people on continuity commitment are motivated by financial gain for the company (Timoti, 2020).

A sense of duty to stay in the job is known as normative commitment (Coyle-Shapiro, 2016; Balassiano and Salles, 2012). In this situation, workers believe they have a duty to the company and should stay there (Andrew, 2017; Mathotaarchchi, 2018). Workers in this group believe that staying is the right thing to do and that they should (Timoti, 2020). Normative commitment tends to rise in response to factors like recognition of individual and organizational productivity, and employee commitment steadily increases when they experience a sense of identification with the organization (Andrew, 2017).

Service Delivery

One important component required to improve customer satisfaction is service delivery (Soegoto, 2017). If done correctly and properly, it helps to enhance income creation for the company and foster customer loyalty. Providing high-quality service delivery becomes a metric for gauging customer satisfaction in any service supply (Soegoto, 2017). According to the author, a service is an action taken by a worker, employee, or business owner for a client or customer in a business or organization, or on a private basis. Since contentment differs from person to person, the author claimed that a service's character and quality

are what determine whether a client is satisfied or not. But according to Krutz and Clow (1998), the service expected depends on what the organization offers. Zeithami, Berry, and Parasuraman (1996) noted that the only way to gauge the quality of a service is to look at how satisfied customers are—that is, if the service lives up to their expectations. They contend that a service is good and of high quality if it satisfies all of the needs and desires of the client; if not, it can be referred to as poor or bad service.

According to Ogonu (2020), providing services is a crucial requirement for any firm. The author defines it as a procedure for providing or performing one's official duties to intended recipients in the most efficient and timely manner possible. Service delivery is a part of business or endeavour that describes the relationship between providers and clients in which the supplier supplies a service and the client either gains or loses value as a result. Therefore, recipients gain more value when services are delivered well (Ogonu, 2020).

Nash and Nash (2004), in Majekodunmi (2012), maintain that service delivery is the act of providing a customer with value, and it is successful when the customer's expectations are fulfilled or surpassed while the company or organization retains its viability. Effective service delivery, in particular, involves performance that meets the requirements, wants, and expectations of the clients (Majekodunmi, 2012). In actuality, Olowu (2002) contends that the establishment of public service was motivated by the provision of services. According to the author, providing services to the public is the main duty of any public administration system. According to Ahmed (2005), service delivery is an ancient idea that serves as a reminder to organizations of their need to provide their clients with the best possible value.

The public and the service provider (government agency) have a contractual connection, according to Egugbo (2020), who only discusses service delivery in respect to public sector entities. The service provider is required under this contractual arrangement to provide the public with services that are as satisfactory as possible in terms of utility, quality, convenience, timeliness, cost, courtesy, communication, etc. (Egugbo, 2020). Vambe (2013) concludes that service delivery is the cornerstone of all government operations. The author claims that services encompass both the supply of material to public goods and intangible deliveries. Put together, Snellen et al. (2002) postulate that service delivery is the act of carrying out, transferring, or delivering goods or values to the intended receiver or achieving the desired outcomes.

Productivity

An organization's competitive edge is strengthened by its productivity. Productivity is defined as the amount and calibre of work done while accounting for the cost of the resources used (Mathis and John, 2003). According to Nosike and Okerekeoti (2022), an organization's productivity is a result of how well its resources are used. Employee output is another indicator of an organization's efficiency (McNamara, 2005). Productivity could be quantified in terms of time, quantity, quality, monetary profits, or community impact (McNamara, 2005). The author went on to say that productivity means figuring out how long it takes an average worker to create a given quantity of labour. Matui (2017) notes that it also describes the amount of time a team of workers devotes to particular tasks, like manufacturing, travel, or idle time spent waiting for supplies or repairing malfunctioning machinery.

The profit of a company is directly impacted by productivity (Nosike and Okerekeoti, 2022). Pay, the appraisal system, training, selection, job design, and compensation are also some of the aspects that impact productivity (Nosike and Okerekeoti, 2022). Nevertheless, if the workforce is highly motivated and effective, productivity can be attained despite the aforementioned constraints (Dobre, 2013).

One of the main strategies for improving organizational success is employee productivity (Hanaysha, 2016). Higher productivity, for example, results in favourable economic growth for the company, significant profitability, and improved social advancement (Sharma and Sharma, 2014). Through cost reductions and improvements in high-quality output, it also tends to optimize organizational competitive advantage (Baily et al, 2005; Hill et al, 2014; Wright, 2004). In that sense, employee productivity can be thought of as an evaluation of an employee's effectiveness (Hanaysha, 2016). Productivity has a direct impact on an organization's earnings (Gummesson, 1998; Sels et al, 2006) and is measured by an employee's output over a given time (Hanaysha, 2016). The output of employees performing comparable

tasks over a given amount of time is used to calculate productivity. Another way to measure it is by looking at how many units of a product or service an employee handles in a given amount of time (Piana, 2001). According to Sharma and Sharma (2014), the length of time an employee spends physically present at work and how effectively they operate during that time are the two main factors used to determine employee productivity.

In this way, productivity is determined by both presence and efficiency at work. Ferreira and Duplessis (2009) provide evidence to support this claim, arguing that productivity may be measured by the amount of time a person spends actively performing their duties and achieving the intended results or outcomes specified in their job description. Employee productivity is essential to every firm since it is the only way for workers to get better or higher pay, better working conditions, and more job prospects (Sharma and Sharma, 2014). For this reason, Cato and Gordon (2009) proposed that employment productivity plays a crucial role in the success of both people and the business.

CONCLUSION

Human resource is the soul and bloodstream of any organization. It is the most important factor in any establishment and therefore must be treated with care. Human resource of any organization needs constant development to galvanize the activities of the organization, positioning it for greatness.

Most public organizations still standing in a collapsing economy have imbibed some of the elements of HRD, such as constant training, development initiatives, coaching, and mentoring. Their investments on these HRD elements have ensured that there is attainment of set goals by these organizations, increase in commitment by staff, tremendous increase in quality of service rendered, and a resounding higher productivity. What is more, development of human resources is the sure catalyst for the success of any organization around the globe.

REFERENCES

- Adelere, M.A. (2017) Effect of staff training and development on organizational performance: Evidence from Nigerian Bottling Company. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter)*, 6(12), 10-24. Doi:10.12816/0041195.
- Agwu, M.O. & Ogiriki, T. (2014) Human resource development and organizational performance in the Nigeria Liquefied National Gas Company Limited, Bonny. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 4(4), 134-146.
- Ahmed, M.Y. (2005) Public service transformation for greater service delivery in A. Goke (ed.) *Nigeria public-service reform; Selected statements of key reform drivers*. Abuja: The Regent Printing and Publishing Ltd.
- Aiya, F., Omoregie, A.N., & Ogbeide, G.I. (2015) *Human resources management practices and organizational performance in Nigeria*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342766230>.
- Akintayo, D.I. (2010) Work-family role conflict and organizational commitment among industrial workers in Nigeria. *Journal of Psychology and Counseling*, 2(1), 1-8.
- Albrecht, S. (2010) *Handbook of employee engagement*. Cheltenham, England: Edward Elgar.
- Allen, J.D. (2007) Mentoring relationships from perspective of the mentor in B.R. Ragins & K.E. Kram (Eds.) *The handbook of mentoring at work: Theory, research and practice*. Thousand Oaks, C.A: Sage Publication.
- Ammons, D.N., & Roenigk, D.J. (2020) Exploring devolved decision authority in performance management regimes: The relevance of perceived and actual decision authority as elements of performance management success. *Public Performance and Management Review*, 15, 28-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15309576.2019.1657918>.
- Andrew, A. (2017) Employees' commitment and its impact on organizational performance. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 5(2), 1-13.

- Antwi, S., & Darkwa, B.F. (2021) From classroom to online: Comparing the effectiveness and student academic performance of classroom learning. *Open Access Library Journal*, 8(7),1-22. Doi: 110.4236/oalib.1107597
- Armstrong, M. (2002) *Human resource management practice: Theory and practice*. Great Britain: The Bath Press Ltd.
- Baily, M.N., Farrell, D., Greenberg, E., Henrich, J.D., Jinjo, N., Jolles, M., & Remes, J. (2005) *Increasing global competition and labour productivity: Lessons from the US automotive industry*. McKensie Global Institute, November, 7.
- Balassiano, M., & Salles, D. (2012) Perceptions of equity and justice and their implications on affective organizational commitment: A confirmatory study in a teaching and research institute. *Brazilian Administrative Review*, 9, 268-286.
- Barkham, J. (2005) Reflections and interpretations on life in Academia: A mentee speaks. *Mentoring and Tutoring*, 13, 331-344.
- Bartlett, K.R. (2001) The relationship between training and organizational commitment: A study in the health care field. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.1001>.
- Beardwell, I., & Holden, L. (2001) *Human resource management: A contemporary approach* (3rd ed). Harlow: Financial Time Prentice Hall.
- Bono, J., Purvanova, R.K., Oowler, A.J., & David, B. (2009) A survey of executive coaching practices. *Personnel Psychology*, 62(2), 361-404.
- Bozeman, B., & Feeney, M.K. (2007) Toward a useful theory of mentoring: A conceptual analysis and critique. *Administrative and Society*, 39(6), 719-739.
- Bratton and Gold (2000) Strategic human resource management: A global perspective in R. Pieper (ed) *International human resources management*. New York: De Gruber.
- Brockbank, A., & McGill, I. (2006) *Facilitating reflective learning through mentoring and coaching*. London: Kogan Page.
- Brooks, I. (2006) *Organizational behaviour: Individuals, groups and organization*. Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
- Camelia, A., & Luminita, R. (2013) The concept of performance-history and forms of manifestation. *Annals of the University of Oradea, Economic Science Series*, 22(1), 1145-1153.
- Cato, S.T., & Gordon, J. (2009) Relationship of the strategic vision alignment to employee productivity and student enrolment. *Research in Higher Education Journal*, 7, 1-20.
- Chukwuma, E.M. (2015) Human resource management challenges in Nigeria under a globalized economy: A study of Innoson vehicles manufacturing company Nigeria Limited. *Journal of Policy and Development Studies*, 9(4), 32-56.
- Colomo, R., & Casado, C. (2006) Mentoring Y coaching: Its perspective. *Journal of Technology Management and Innovation*, 3,131-139.
- Commeiras, N., & Fournier, C. (2001) Critical evaluation of Porter organizational commitment questionnaire: Implications for researchers. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 21(3), 239-245.
- Coyle-Shapiro, M.A. (2016) Serving two organizations: Exploring the employment relationship of contracted employee. *Human Resource Management*, 45, 561-583.
- Dernovsek, D. (2008) *Creating highly engaged and committed employee starts at the top and ends at the bottom line*. Credit Union Magazine. Credit Union National Association, Inc.
- Dim, E., Emeakayi, H.C., & Arua, N.M. (2019) Effect of employee training on performance of selected Multinational Corporations in Nigeria. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 2(2), 53-71.
- Dobre, O. (2013) Employee motivation and organizational performance. *Review of Applied Socio-Economic Research*, 5, 53.

- Dost, M.K., Laqman, M., Ahmed, Z., Shafi, N., & Shaheen, W.A., (2011) Impact of employee commitment on organizational performance. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(3), 87-98.
- Egugbo, C.C. (2020) Public service delivery in Nigeria's fourth republic" Issues, challenges and prospects for social-economic development. *Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law*, 17, 72-80.
- Eze, F.O. (2010) *Human resource management: Strategy, theory and applications*. Enugu: Chaneks Enterprises Nig.
- Ezeani, E.O. (2002) "Human resources utilization in the Nigerian local government system: Problems and remedies" in E.O. Ezeani and B.C. Nwankwo (eds) *Human resources management in the local government system in Nigeria*. Nsukka: AP Express Publishers.
- Feldman, D., & Lankan, M.J. (2005) Executive coaching: A review and agenda for future research. *Journal of Management*, 31(6), 829-848.
- Ferreira, A., & Du Plessis, T. (2009) Effect of online social networking on employee productivity. *South African Journal of Information management*, 11(1), 1-11.
- Gelaidan, M.H., & Ahmad, H. (2013) The factors affecting employee commitment to change in public sector: Evidence from Yemen. *International Business Research*, 6, 75-87. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ibr.vbr.vbn3p75>.
- Gill, A., & Carrillo, F. (2013) La creation de conocimiento en las organizaciones a partir det aprendizaje. *Intangible Capital*, 9(3), 730-753. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3926/ic.418>.
- Griffin, L.L., & Ayers, S.F. (2005) Chapter 1: Introduction: The roles and process of mentoring. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 24, 297-301.
- Gruzina, Y., Irina, F., & Wadim, S. (2021) Dynamics of human capital development in economic development cycles. *Economies*, 9:67. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies9020067>.
- Gul, Z. (2015) Impact of employee commitment on organizational development. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(2), 117-124.
- Gummesson, E. (1998) Productivity, quality and relationship marketing in service operations. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 10(1), 4-5.
- Gungor, P. (2011) The relationship between reward management system and procedural. *Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 10(3), 1510-1520.
- Hanaysha, J. (2016) Improving employee productivity through work engagement: Empirical evidence from higher education sector. *Management Science Letters*, 6, 61-70. doi:10.5267/j.msl.2015.11.006.
- Hannafey, F.T., & Vitulano, L.A. (2013) Ethics and executive coaching: An agency theory approach. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 115(3), 599-604.
- Ivancevich, J.M. (2010) *Human resource management*. Irwin: McGraw-Hill
- Joiner, T.A., Bartram, T., & Garreffa, T. (2004) The effects of mentoring on perceived career success, commitment and turnover intentions. *The Journal of American Academy of Business*, 5, 164-170.
- Jones, R.G., George, M.J., & Hill, W.C. (2000) *Contemporary management*. 2nd Edition. McGraw-Hill Companies Inc.
- Kampa-Kolesch, S., & Anderson, M.Z., (2001) Executive coaching: A comprehensive review of the literature. *Consulting Psychology Journal*, 53(4), 205-228. <http://dx.doi.org/10.037/1061.4087.53.4.205>.
- Kurtz, D.L., & Clow, K.E. (1998) *Services marketing*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Latham, G.P., Borgogni, L., & Pettitta, L. (2008) Goal setting and performance management in the public sector. *International Public Management Journal*, 11(4), 385-403.
- Majekodunmi, A. (2012) The state of local government and service delivery in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Africa's Public Service Delivery and Performance Review*, 1(3), 84-98. Doi:10.4102/apsdpr.vli3.37.

- Markos, & Sridhevi (2010) Employee engagement: The key to improving performance. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(12).
- Mathis, R.L., & John, H.J. (2003) *Human resources management* (11th ed.). Mason, OH: Thomson/South-Western.
- Mathotaarachchi, P.G., Indikasampathl, K., Pereraaknj, S. (2018) Impact of employees' commitment on sustained productivity: With reference to government institutions sector in Sri Lanka. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, ISSN: 2278-487X, P-ISSN:2319-7668.
- Matui, J.K. (2017) Employee productivity on organizational performance in the Kenyan banking sector: A case of Kenya Commercial Bank. Unpublished research project submitted to the School of Business in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Master of Business Administration, Kenyatta University.
- Mayfield, J., & Mayfield, M. (2007) The effects of leader communication on a worker's intent to stay: An investigation using structural equation modeling. *Human Performance*, 20(2), 85-102. Doi:10.1080/08959280701332018.
- McNamara, C. (2005) *Field guide to leadership and supervision for non-profit staff* (2nd ed.) Amazon.
- Meyer, J.P., & Elyse, R.M. (2010) Employee commitment and well-being: A critical review, theoretical framework and research agenda. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 77(2), 323-337.
- Ministry of Human Resources Development (MHRD (N.D) Staff development: Meaning, objectives, process and methods. Govt of India. Doi: 1541503939Note_StaffDevelopment (1).pdf.
- Minor, M. (2007) *Meningkatkan Kinerja Tim melalui Coaching dan counseling*. Jakarta: PPM.
- Monika, M., & Nischay, K.U. (2017) Examining the influence of mentoring on organizational commitment and performance. <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Murray, M. (2006) *Innovations in performance improvement with mentoring: Handbook of human performance technology*. San Francise: Pfeiffer, 455-477.
- Noe, R.A. (2008) *Human resource management* (6th Ed) USA: Mcgraw Hill Higher Education.
- Noraazian & Khalip, M. (2016) A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6 (12), 16-23.
- Nosike, C.J., & Okerekeoti, C.U. (2022) Employee productivity and organizational performance: Evidence from Pharmaceutical Firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 6(4), 108-116.
- Nuryanti, B.L., Putri, W.D., & Masharyono (2018) Effect of training and empowerment in improving job satisfaction. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 117, 265-268.
- Nwanolue, B.O.G., & Iwuoha, V.C. (2012) The Conundrum and contradictions of human resource administration in contemporary Nigerian civil service: A focus on Enugu State Civil Service Commission. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(10), 56-68.
- Obadan (2000) *Improving productivity in Nigeria economy through effective planning and research*. Ibadan: National Centre for Economic Management and Administration.
- Obisi, C. (1996) *Industrial relations*. Ibadan: Freeman Productions.
- Ogonu, J.C. (2020) Relationship between staff motivation and service delivery in libraries of higher education in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Information*, 13, 1-8.
- Oladimeji, M.S., & Sowemimo, O.Z. (2020) The effect of mentoring on employee job performance in the Nigerian service sector. *Organizacijų vadyba" Sisteminiai Tyrimai* 2020. 84. <https://doi.org/10.1515/mosr-2020-0011>.
- Olowu, D. (2002) Public service delivery. In L. Ademolekun (ed.). *Public administration in Africa: Main issues and selected country studies*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd.
- Olu-Ogunleye, I., Akinbode, J., Oyelude, O., & Ogunleye, O. (2022) Human capital management and employees performance in Nigerian Local Governments. *UNIBEN Journal of Human Resources Management*, 1(1), 100-113.

- Onafadeji, A.O., Ogunyemi, F.F., & Alarape, B.A. (2017) Human resource management and employee performance in Federal University of Technology, Akure. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(4), 95-104. Doi: 10.9790/487X-19040295104.
- Onah, C.C., Asadu, I., Okafor, I.C., Aduma, A., Eneh, M.I., & Amujiri, B. (2023) Exploring the imperative of human capital development as a pathway for the achievement of sustainable development: A theoretical discourse. *Journal of Xi'an Shiyou University, Natural Science Edition*, 19(6), 138-154.
- Onasanya, C.M.D. (2006) *Effective personnel management and industrial relations* (1st Ed). Lagos: Centre for Management and Development.
- Orga, C.C., & Ogbo, A.I. (2012) Evaluating the challenges of human resource management in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(13), 78-85.
- Osiobe, E.U. (2021) A literature review and overview of performance management: A guide to the field. *Sumerianz Journal of Business Management and Marketing*, 4(1), 1-11
- Peretomode, V.F., & Peretomode, O. (2001) *Human resources management*. Lagos: Obaroh and Ogbinaka Publishers Ltd.
- Pertin, R.D. (2011) *Mentoring: A business strategy that works*. Ebook: Pertin management Mentors Inc.
- Peterson, D.B., & Hicks, M.D. (2010) *The leader as coach: Strategies for coaching and developing others*. Minneapolis, M.N: Personnel Decisions.
- Piana, V. (2001) Productivity. <http://www.economicwebinstitute.org/glossary/practvt.htm>.
- Piwowar-Sulej, K. (2021) Human resources development as an element of sustainable HRM-with the focus on production engineers. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278:124008.
- Ragins, B.R., & Scandura, T.A. (1999) Burden or blessing: Expected costs and benefits of being a mentor. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 20 (4), 493-509.
- Rhoades, L., Eisenberger, R., & Armeli, S. (2001) Affective commitment to the organization: The contribution of perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(5), 825-836.
- Sarah, P., Bello, O., & Erunke, C.E. (2022) An overview of the challenges of human resource management and organizational performance in Nigeria. *Human Discourse*, 2(1), 1-2.
- Saygan, N.F. (2011) Relationship between affective commitment and organizational silence: A conceptual discussion. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanity Studies*, 3(2).
- Sels, L., De Winne, S., Delmotte, J., Maes, J., Faems, D., & Forrier, A. (2006) Linking HRM and small business performance: An examination of the impact of HRM intensity on the productivity and financial performance of small business. *Small Business Economics*, 26(1), 83-101.
- Sharma, M.S., & Sharma, M.V. (2014) Employee engagement to enhance productivity in current Scenario. *International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management*, 3(4), 595-604.
- Shea, S. (2007) A good mentor has helped me realize my potentials as a nurse. *Nursing Standard*, 21(20), 27-37.
- Snellen, I.T.M., & Vande Donk, W.B. (2002) *Public administration in an information age*. Amsterdam: IOS Press.
- Soegoto, E.S. (2017) The influence of motivation on quality service delivery in decentralized Indonesia. *Jurnal Bisnis & Manajemen*, xviii (2), 83-89.
- Sridarran, L. (2016) Impact of work place stress on employees' job performance: Special reference to Apparel Industry in Batticaloa District, Sri Lanka. *Bus. Manag.*, 4(3), 63-66.
- Stock, T., Micheal, O., Sascha, K., & Holger, K. (2018) Industry 4.0 as enabler for a sustainable development: A qualitative assessment of its ecological and social potential. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 118:254-67.
- Stone, R. (2002) *Human resource management*. 4th Edition. Milton, Australia: Wiley Art Department.
- Swanson, R. (2001) Human resource development and its underlying theory. *Human Resource Development International*, 4(3), 299-312.

- Tharenou, P., Saks, A.M., & Moore, C. (2007) A review and critique of research on training and organizational-level outcomes. *Human Resource Management Review*, 17, 251-273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2007.07.004>.
- Timoti, K. (2020) *Employee commitment on organizational performance: A review of literature*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346425419>.
- Tumwesigye, G. (2010) The relationship between perceived organizational support and turnover intentions in a developing country: The mediating role of organizational commitment. *African Journal of Business Management*, (6), 942-952.
- Tzafirir, & Baruch (2005) Training and development in relation to performance. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 236-290.
- Umoh, G.I., Mama, E.A., Wokocha, H. (2014) Employee benefits and continuance commitment in Nigerian manufacturing industry. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*.
- Utrilla, P.N., Grande, F.A., & Lorenzo, D. (2015) The effects of coaching in employees and organizational performance: The Spanish case. *Intangible Capital*, 11(2), 166-189. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3926/ic.586>.
- Vambe, J. T. (2013) Improving public service delivery in Nigeria through ethics, integrity and professionalism. *Research Journal of Social Science and Management*, 3(4), 126-137.
- Wang, C.L., Indridasson, T., & Saunders, M.N.K. (2010) Affective and continuance commitment in public private partnership. *Employee Relations*, 32(4), 396-417.
- Wright, A. (2004) *Reward management in context*. CIPD Publishing.
- Zeithami, V.A., Berry, L.L., & Parasuraman, A. (1996) The behavioural consequences of service quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 60(2), 31-46. Doi: 10.2307/125192.
- Zheng, W., Sharan,K., & Wei, J. (2010) New development of organizational commitment: A critical review (1960-2009). *African Journal of Business Management*, 4 (1), 12-20.